

The wave equation approach to the continuity equation in quantum mechanics

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Abstract: Matter, when in motion, possess wave nature and it is well perceived fact. A mathematical quantity that describes the wave nature of particle is called as wave function and the square of modulus of wave function is interpreted as probability density function. The probabilistic interpretation of square of modulus of wave function could be drawn from the continuity equation in quantum mechanics [1]. In present work, we've alternatively and non-relativistically derived the continuity equation in quantum mechanics by using classical wave equation.

Keywords: Continuity equation; wave equation; lagrangian; wave function; probability.

PACS Numbers: 02.50.Cw; 03.65.-w; 03.65.Ge; 03.75.-b

1. Introduction:

The *continuity equation in quantum mechanics* (CEQM) is given as,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where, $\rho = |\psi|^2$ and $\vec{J}$ is a probability current given as $\vec{J} = \frac{\hbar}{2mi} (\psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^*)$ here ψ (being a wave function) is a function of 3-Dimensional space and time i.e. $\psi = \psi(x, y, z, t)$. Eq. (1) represents the instantaneous flow of probability current. In short words, it represents the conservation of probability [2, 3]. In simplest way, the derivation of Schrodinger equation begins by considering a plane wave which is solution of the wave equation [4, 5]. The 3-Dimensional wave equation is given as,

$$\nabla^2 \psi = \frac{1}{v^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} \quad (2)$$

Here, we may take v as the velocity of particle and ψ being a solution of Eq. (2) describes the wave nature of particle and we call it as wave function of a particle [4, 5]. Let m be the mass of particle and let U be the potential energy of particle. Since we are dealing non-relativistically therefore, the kinetic energy of particle is $K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and we write

non-relativistic lagrangian for particle having kinetic energy $K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and potential energy U as,

$$\mathcal{L} = K - U = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 - U \quad (3)$$

Now, from Eq. (2) and (3) we write,

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}m \left(\frac{\left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} \right)}{\nabla^2 \psi} \right) - U \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) can be written as,

$$\mathcal{L}\nabla^2\psi = \frac{m}{2} \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial t^2} - U\nabla^2\psi \quad (5)$$

The complex conjugate of the Eq. (5) is,

$$\mathcal{L}\nabla^2\psi^* = \frac{m}{2} \frac{\partial^2\psi^*}{\partial t^2} - U\nabla^2\psi^* \quad (6)$$

Multiplying Eq. (5) by ψ^* and Eq. (6) by ψ we get,

$$\mathcal{L}\psi^*\nabla^2\psi = \frac{m}{2} \psi^* \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial t^2} - U\psi^*\nabla^2\psi \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{L}\psi\nabla^2\psi^* = \frac{m}{2} \psi \frac{\partial^2\psi^*}{\partial t^2} - U\psi\nabla^2\psi^* \quad (8)$$

Subtracting Eq. (8) from Eq. (7) we get,

$$\mathcal{L}(\psi^*\nabla^2\psi - \psi\nabla^2\psi^*) = \frac{m}{2} \left(\psi^* \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial t^2} - \psi \frac{\partial^2\psi^*}{\partial t^2} \right) - U(\psi^*\nabla^2\psi - \psi\nabla^2\psi^*) \quad (9)$$

Rearranging terms of Eq. (9) and using $\mathcal{L} + U = K$ we get,

$$K(\psi^*\nabla^2\psi - \psi\nabla^2\psi^*) = \frac{m}{2} \left(\psi^* \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial t^2} - \psi \frac{\partial^2\psi^*}{\partial t^2} \right) \quad (10)$$

Observe,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\psi^* \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} - \psi \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial t} \right) = \left(\psi^* \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} - \psi \frac{\partial^2 \psi^*}{\partial t^2} \right) \quad (11)$$

Therefore, from Eq. (10) and (11) we can write,

$$K(\psi^* \nabla^2 \psi - \psi \nabla^2 \psi^*) = \frac{m}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\psi^* \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} - \psi \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial t} \right) \quad (12)$$

If $i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ operates on plane wave (wave function) then we get corresponding total energy eigenvalue E of particle and therefore we write,

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = E\psi \quad (13)$$

The complex conjugate of Eq. (13) is,

$$-i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial t} = E\psi^* \quad (14)$$

Multiplying Eq. (13) by ψ^* and Eq. (14) by ψ and adding both we get,

$$i\hbar \psi^* \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} - i\hbar \psi \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial t} = 2E|\psi|^2 \quad (15)$$

From Eq. (12) and (15) we write,

$$K(\psi^* \nabla^2 \psi - \psi \nabla^2 \psi^*) = \frac{mE}{i\hbar} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (|\psi|^2) \quad (16)$$

Here, $K = \frac{1}{2} m v^2$ can be written as $K = \frac{P^2}{2m}$, recall the momentum of particle is given as $P = \frac{h}{\lambda} = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{\lambda}$ where λ is De Broglie wavelength of particle. Therefore, we write,

$$K = \frac{2\pi^2\hbar^2}{m\lambda^2} \quad (17)$$

Arranging Eq. (16) and (17) and we write,

$$\frac{2i\pi^2\hbar^2}{m^2\lambda^2} (\psi^* \nabla^2 \psi - \psi \nabla^2 \psi^*) = \frac{E}{\hbar} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (|\psi|^2) \quad (18)$$

Observe,

$$\nabla \cdot (\psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^*) = (\psi^* \nabla^2 \psi - \psi \nabla^2 \psi^*) \quad (19)$$

From Eq. (18) and (19) we write,

$$\frac{2i\pi^2 \hbar^2}{m^2 \lambda^2} \nabla \cdot (\psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^*) = \frac{E}{\hbar} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (|\psi|^2) \quad (20)$$

Recall the expression for probability current vector,

$$\vec{J} = \frac{\hbar}{2mi} (\psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^*) \quad (21)$$

From Eq. (20) and (21) we write,

$$\frac{2i\pi^2 \hbar^2}{m^2 \lambda^2} \frac{2mi}{\hbar} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = \frac{E}{\hbar} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (|\psi|^2) \quad (22)$$

Consider the L.H.S. of Eq. (22),

$$L.H.S. = \frac{2i\pi^2 \hbar^2}{m^2 \lambda^2} \frac{2mi}{\hbar} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = \frac{-4\pi^2 \hbar}{m \lambda^2} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} \quad (23)$$

Recall from Einstein and De Broglie relation that $E = \hbar \omega$, where ω being an angular frequency of particle and $\omega = 2\pi \vartheta$ where ϑ is frequency [5]. Therefore, $\hbar = \frac{E}{2\pi \vartheta}$ substituting this value in Eq. (23) we write,

$$L.H.S. = \frac{-4\pi^2 E}{2\pi \vartheta m \lambda^2} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = \frac{-2\pi E}{m \lambda (\vartheta \lambda)} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} \quad (24)$$

But, $\vartheta \lambda = v$, where v is a velocity of particle. Substituting this value in Eq. (24) we write,

$$L.H.S. = \frac{-2\pi E}{mv \lambda} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} \quad (25)$$

Here, $mv = P = \frac{h}{\lambda}$, substituting this value in Eq. (25) we write,

$$L.H.S. = \frac{-2\pi E \lambda}{h \lambda} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = \frac{-E}{\hbar} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} \quad (26)$$

From Eq. (22) and (26) we write,

$$\frac{-E}{\hbar} \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = \frac{E}{\hbar} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (|\psi|^2) \quad (27)$$

Eq. (27) implies,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = 0 \quad (28)$$

Where, $\rho = |\psi|^2$. Eq. (28) represents the CEQM.

2. Conclusion:

It follows from above discussion that CEQM can also be derived using classical wave equation. For derivation of Schrodinger equation, the approach which was taken by Schrodinger himself involved the classical wave equation [4]. Owing to this fact, we've used the classical wave equation for deriving CEQM. The probabilistic interpretation of $|\psi|^2$ could be drawn from CEQM. In this work to derive CEQM, we've just considered classical wave equation and Einstein-De Broglie relations and we see that the probabilistic interpretation of $|\psi|^2$ comes into being automatically as if we've used Schrodinger equation itself for this purpose.

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